

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of alcohols by piperidinium chlorochromate

H. N. Sheikh*, Madhu Sharma and B. L. Kalsotra

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Baba Saheb Ambedkar Road, Jammu-180 006, India

E-mail : hnsheikh@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 19 May 2005, accepted 14 July 2005

Piperidinium chlorochromate is an efficient oxidizing agent for oxidation of primary alcohols to aldehydes. Kinetics of oxidation of alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds have been studied in aqueous-acetic acid medium in presence of perchloric acid. The reaction shows first order kinetics each in [PipCC] and $[H^+]$. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics have been observed with respect to [alcohol]. The rate of oxidation decreases with increase in dielectric constant of solvent indicating ion-dipole interaction. The oxidation of alcohols by piperidinium chlorochromate gives corresponding aldehydes in good yields.

A wide variety of chromium(VI) reagents viz. pyridinium chlorochromate (Corey's reagent or PCC), pyridinium bromochromate, 2,2-bipyridinium chlorochromate, imidazolium chlorochromate, quinolinium fluorochromate, quinolinium dichromate and isoquinolinium chlorochromate have been used as mild and selective oxidizing agents in synthetic organic chemistry¹. In view of the increasing importance of pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC), pyridinium fluorochromate, quinolinium chlorochromate and 2,2-bipyridinium chlorochromate in organic synthesis as potential and selective oxidizing agents an attempt was made to extend the study to other halochromates². We report in this paper, the kinetics of oxidation of primary alcohols by piperidinium chlorochromate in aqueous acetic acid medium.

Results and discussion

Oxidation of the aliphatic alcohols by piperidinium chlorochromate proceeded smoothly at 25°C and resulted in the formation of the corresponding aldehydes. Stoichiometric studies revealed that 3 moles of alcohol consumed 2 moles of piperidinium chlorochromate in accordance with eq. (1),

Effect of oxidant and substrate :

At fixed $[H^+]$ with reductant in excess, plot of $\log [PipCC]$ against time is linear indicating first order in $[PipCC]$. The first order rate constants are independent of initial concentration of PipCC (Table 1). The rate of

Table 1. Effect of concentration of reactants on reaction rate at 298 K in acid media

$10^2 [Ethanol] \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$10^3 [PipCC] \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$10^3 k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.0	2.0	1.66
2.0	2.0	3.13
2.0	2.0	3.22
3.0	2.0	5.03
4.0	2.0	5.83
5.0	2.0	7.54
6.0	2.0	8.91
5.0	3.0	7.61
5.0	4.0	7.75
5.0	5.0	7.16
5.0	6.0	7.02

oxidation increases with increase in concentration of alcohol (Table 1). Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[alcohol]$ gives straight line, which does not pass through origin indicating Michaelis-Menten type kinetics.

A positive intercept shows that a 1 : 1 complex is formed prior to the rate-limiting step between PipCC and alcohol.

Effect of perchloric acid :

Rate of reaction increases with increase in perchloric acid concentration (Table 2). This shows that protonated Cr^{VI} species is formed during reaction. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ gives a straight line with slope ~ 1 , indicating first order dependence on $[H^+]$.

Table 2. Effect of concentration of acid on reaction rates at 298 K
[Ethanol] = 0.05 mol dm⁻³, [PipCC] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³, acetic acid = 60% (v/v)

[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8
10 ³ k _{obs} s ⁻¹	3.26	4.89	6.50	7.16	8.94	11.01	14.06

Effect of solvent composition :

The rate of acid catalysed oxidation of alcohol with PipCC increases with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (Table 3). This is due to polar character of the transition state as compared to the reactants. The plot of log k_{obs} vs 1/D (dielectric constant) is linear with positive slope suggesting an interaction between a positive ion and a dipole³.

Table 3. Effect of concentration of solvent on reaction rates at 298 K

[Ethanol] = 0.05 mol dm⁻³, [PipCC] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³

Acetic acid-water (% v/v)	30	40	50	60	70
Dielectric constant	72.0	63.3	56.0	45.5	38.5
10 ³ k _{obs} s ⁻¹	2.81	3.48	4.87	7.20	12.75

Effect of piperidine :

There is no effect of piperidine on rate of reaction, indicating that PipCC is not hydrolysed in the reaction. Further, this indicates stability of PipCC during the reaction. The kinetic experiments were performed with five different aliphatic primary alcohols (Table 4).

Table 4. Reaction rates of the alcohols at 298 K

[Alcohol] = 0.05 mol dm⁻³, [PipCC] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³, acetic acid = 60% (v/v)

Alcohol	k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	Product	% Yield
Methanol	5.12 × 10 ⁻³	Methanal	77
Ethanol	7.82 × 10 ⁻³	Ethanal	75
Propanol	9.80 × 10 ⁻³	Propanal	78
n-Butanol	12.00 × 10 ⁻³	n-Butanal	71
n-Pentanol	14.50 × 10 ⁻³	n-Pentanal	70

Mechanism based on all observed experimental results :

The reaction proceeds by the formation of PipCC-ester intermediate (Scheme 1) :

Scheme 1

The rate law derived based on above mechanism, is as follows :

$$\text{Rate of reaction} = \frac{-d[\text{C}]}{dt} \propto [\text{C}]$$

$$= k [\text{C}]$$

Concentration of complex, [C] can be calculated by applying steady state concept.

Rate of formation of complex = Rate of decomposition of complex

$$k_1 [\text{A}] [\text{PipCC}]_{\text{eqm}} = k_{-1} [\text{C}] + k [\text{C}]$$

where [PipCC]_{eqm} is equilibrium concentration of PipCC.

$$\text{Since } [\text{PipCC}]_{\text{total}} = [\text{PipCC}]_{\text{eqm}} + [\text{C}]$$

$$\text{Therefore, } [\text{PipCC}]_{\text{eqm}} = [\text{PipCC}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{C}]$$

Hence,

$$k_1 [\text{A}] \{[\text{PipCC}]_t - [\text{C}]\} = (k_{-1} + k) [\text{C}]$$

$$k_1 [\text{A}] [\text{PipCC}]_t - k_1 [\text{A}] [\text{C}] = (k_{-1} + k) [\text{C}]$$

Therefore, $\{k_{-1} + k + k_1 [\text{A}]\} [\text{C}] = k_1 [\text{A}] [\text{PipCC}]_t$

Hence,

$$[\text{C}] = \frac{k_1 [\text{A}] [\text{PipCC}]_t}{k_{-1} + k + k_1 [\text{A}]}$$

$$= \frac{[A] [\text{PipCC}]_t}{k'_{-1} + k} + [A]$$

$$= \frac{[A] [\text{PipCC}]_t}{K_m + [A]}$$

Hence,

$$\text{Rate} = k [C]$$

$$= \frac{k [A] [\text{PipCC}]_t}{K_m + [A]}$$

$$= k_1 [\text{PipCC}]_t$$

$$= k_{\text{obs}} [\text{PipCC}]_t$$

where,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k [A]}{K_m + [A]}$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{K_m}{k} \frac{1}{[A]} + \frac{1}{k}$$

Therefore, K_m can be calculated by slope/intercept of plot $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[A]$.

The rate data obtained satisfactorily supports the above mechanism. The values of K_m and k obtained from the plot are $4.824 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $2.35 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. An increase in the proportion of acetic acid in solvent mixture of aqueous-acetic acid increases the rate. This is because the chromate-ester intermediate would be better stabilized in the presence of solvents of low polarity i.e. decrease of solvent polarity would increase the rate. The variation in the rate among the higher alcohols is because the formation of chromate-ester intermediate, is likely to be influenced by structural changes⁴.

The mechanism involving chromium(V) and chromium(IV) as the only intermediates has been preferred in the past but in recent years mechanism which involves chromium(II) also as an intermediate has been widely accepted as correct mechanism for the chromium(VI) oxidation of many organic compounds⁵. According to the accepted current mechanism chromium(IV) formed oxidizes the organic substrate and gets reduced to chromium(II); chromium(II) reduces chromium(VI) yielding chromium(III) and chromium(V). Chromium(V) oxidises another molecule of alcohol⁶.

Experimental

Preparation of piperidinium chlorochromate :

To an ice-cooled solution of chromium trioxide (5 g, 0.05 mol) dissolved in 9.2 ml of 6 M hydrochloric acid was added 4.2 ml of piperidine in small portions with constant stirring. The resulting solution was kept in an ice bath for about 6 h. The yellowish orange complex so formed was filtered and dried *in vacuo*; yield 6.2 g (56%); m.p. 121°C; pH of 10^{-3} M aqueous solution 3.75; molar conductivity $394 \text{ mho cm}^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. PipCC is soluble in water, alcohol, dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulphoxide, acetone. The structure of PipCC was confirmed by elemental analyses (Found : Cr, 23.01; Cl, 15.62; C, 32.19; H, 5.01. Calcd. : Cr, 23.46; Cl, 15.99; C, 32.59; H, 5.91) and the infrared spectrum (KBr) which exhibited bands at 3049, 2958, 2867, 2505, 2387, 1843, 1579, 1471, 1454, 1422, 1308, 1275, 1160, 1115, 1078, 1022, 951, 900, 859, 811, 544, 439, 415, 370 cm^{-1} characteristic of various groups in PipCC. Purity of PipCC was checked by estimating chromium(VI) iodometrically. The solid is not appreciably hygroscopic and can be stored for extended periods at room temperature without any change.

The alcohols were distilled before use and middle fractions collected. Acetic acid was purified by the reported procedure⁷. HClO_4 (Thomas Baker, 70% reagent grade), CrO_3 (99% Merck, India) and doubly distilled water was used.

Oxidation of alcohol :

In a typical experiment for product analysis, ethanol (4.6 g, 0.1 mol) and PipCC (0.443 g, 0.2 mol) are dissolved in 100 ml of the solvent (60% v/v aqueous acetic acid) and kept in the dark for 12 h to ensure completion of the reaction with TLC monitoring. A saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm^{-3} hydrochloric acid was added to above solution and then kept for 12 h in refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from alcohol and again weighed. The yield of DNP was 75% after recrystallization. That oxidation of ethanol by PipCC in aqueous acetic acid gave acetaldehyde in high yield was confirmed by reacting known excess of PipCC with ethanol (0.05 mol) and estimating unreacted chromium(VI). The corresponding aldehydes were characterized by chemical methods and TLC techniques.

Kinetics of oxidation :

The kinetics of the reaction was followed by conduct-

ing the reaction under pseudo-first order condition by keeping an excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of alcohol over PipCC. The solvent was 60% v/v aqueous acetic acid in the presence of perchloric acid. The progress of the reactions were followed by measuring the decrease in absorbance at $\lambda = 350$ nm at known intervals on an ELICO Spectral Treats Spectrophotometer, using a 1 cm matched quartz cell. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The reactions were usually followed up to not less than 80% completion at constant temperature. The reaction mixture was homogenous in solvent composition and PipCC remained stable over the period of kinetic investigation. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} were computed from the linear plots of $\log [\text{PipCC}]$ versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that rate constants were reproducible within ± 4 .

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